

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGY IN A SCIENTIFIC TEXT

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Annotation. *The main goal of this research is to identify the specific features of phraseology in a scientific text. The objectives of the study include theoretical justification of the concept of a phraseological unit and its role in a scientific text, identifying the main problems associated with translating such units. A number of scientific papers have been written on this topic. As an example, the views of various scientists on this concept are given.*

Key words: *phrase, phraseology, stable combinations, word combinations, phraseological units, translation, scientific text, scientific phraseology.*

Kirish. Phraseology is an important and multifaceted area of linguistics that studies stable phrases and expressions that have a special meaning and function in language. In the context of a scientific text, phraseology acquires special significance, since it is in these texts that specific information is formed and transmitted, requiring accuracy, clarity and brevity. Scientific texts, as a rule, differ from other types of discourse in their structure, style and purpose, which determines the specific features of the phraseology used in them.

Scientific text, as a form of communication, serves to convey knowledge, research results and discoveries. In this context, phraseological units play a key role, as they allow authors not only to express complex ideas and concepts, but also to make the text more accessible for perception. Set expressions and terms used in scientific literature often have a highly specialized meaning and require certain preparation from the reader for their correct understanding. Thus, phraseology in a scientific text becomes not just a means of expressing thoughts, but also a tool that helps to form scientific thinking and promotes the exchange of knowledge in various fields of science.

As we know, at first glance, the use of phraseological combinations is a rare phenomenon, extremely uncharacteristic for the scientific style of speech. This is due to the fact that a scientific text does not assume the presence of any forms of expression, it is alien to the demonstration of feelings and emotions, close to rational methods of conveying content. According to A.N. Vasil'yeva: "the main functional feature of the scientific text is "a contextless and unambiguous expression of

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thoughts, devoid of connotations” [1; p. 82], while phraseological units are highly “connotative”.

One of the key features of phraseology in a scientific text is its lexical component. Scientific texts are usually saturated with terms and specialized vocabulary, which requires authors to be able to accurately select words and expressions to describe complex phenomena and processes. Lexical features of phraseology in a scientific text can include both set expressions and terminological combinations that help create a clear and logical structure of the text. In addition, it is necessary to take into account that many phraseological units can have different meanings depending on the context, which adds complexity to their use.

The semantic features of phraseology in scientific texts also deserve attention. Scientific language requires a high degree of precision and unambiguity in the transmission of information, so the use of phraseological units should be carefully considered. Some expressions may have cultural or historical connotations that may not be obvious to a reader who does not have special knowledge in this area. Therefore, the study of the semantics of phraseological units in a scientific text is an important part of the analysis of scientific communication.

As noted by E.V. Leskova, “one of the main features of phraseology in scientific text is its desire for precision and unambiguity. Scientific disciplines require researchers to strictly adhere to terminology, which is often based on established phraseological constructions. For example, in the field of medicine or physics, there are specific terms that are used to describe certain phenomena or processes. These terms can be part of broader phraseological units that help create a clear and understandable description of the object under study. Thus, phraseology in a scientific text not only decorates the language, but also serves as an important tool for conveying knowledge and ideas” [4; p. 34].

In addition, according to L.M. Ibatulina, “phraseological units in scientific texts are often used to create coherence and consistency in presentation. Scientific works, as a rule, have a clear structure, and the use of set expressions helps authors smoothly move from one thought to another. For example, phrases such as “in connection with the above”, “therefore” or “in conclusion” serve as connecting elements that help the reader better understand the logic of the presentation. This is especially important in scientific texts, where not only the content, but also the form of presentation play a key role in the perception of information” [3; p. 517].

Phraseology can also serve as a stylistic element in scientific writing. Although scientific style is usually characterized by formality and rigor, the use of

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phraseological units can add expressiveness and dynamism to the text. For example, the use of metaphors or comparisons, even in a scientific context, can make the presentation more interesting. However, it is important to remember that such elements should be used with caution so as not to distract the reader from the main idea. In this context, phraseology becomes a kind of balancing element that helps to maintain scientific rigor without losing the reader's interest [4].

Such stylistic groups of phraseological units as terms or speech clichés (i.e., strictly “scientific” phraseological units) are the most “readable”, practically transparent in terms of meaning. A striking example of this is the phraseological combinations of legal (to provide assistance, to reach an agreement, to recover moral damages, to satisfy a request, to file a cassation appeal, to confiscate property) [2; p.151] and medical (to put on feet, medical confidentiality, goose liver, barking cough, wisdom tooth) [5; p. 248] orientations, which are often encountered in texts when working with the relevant specialties.

In conclusion, phraseology in a scientific text is a multifaceted phenomenon that plays an important role in the transfer of knowledge, the creation of coherence and consistency of presentation, as well as in the stylistic design of the text. Set expressions help authors express their thoughts more accurately and concisely, which is especially important in the context of scientific activity, where accuracy and clarity are of paramount importance. The diversity of phraseological units, their dynamic change and specificity depending on the field of knowledge make phraseology an integral part of scientific language, which emphasizes its importance in modern scientific discourse.

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